

**ANATOMICAL, PHARMACEUTICAL AND CLINICAL
TERMINOLOGY IN LATIN CLASSES**

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Abstract. The article “Anatomical, pharmaceutical and clinical terminology in Latin classes” talks about the interdisciplinary branch of knowledge - terminology. Three leading terminological subsystems are examined in more detail: anatomical-histological terminology, pharmaceutical terminology and clinical terminology. The article discusses the principles of the model for compiling Latin terms and their Greek doublets (TE) in the names of functional disorders, in the names of pathological processes and conditions, in pharmaceutical terminology and recipe

Key words: Latin language, medical terminology, terminology, term element (TE)

The object of study in the course of medical Latin is words and phrases that denote special concepts of medical science. Such words and word combinations are called terms, and their combination forms medical terminology - professional medical workers. Medical terminology has evolved throughout the history of medicine and continues to evolve along with medical science. A medical specialist must competently use the constantly updated professional knowledge and understand the laws that define military terms. Doctors from any country, along with terms based on their native language, use a lot of international, generally accepted terms based on ancient Greek and Latin. These terms are of a universal nature, have come into general use and are understandable to professionals regardless of their nationality.

Such international terms constitute the main fund of medical science. The leading role of the ancient Greek and Latin languages in the formation of international medical terminology is explained historically, in the unique sense that There was an ancient purpose of Ancient Greece and Ancient Rome for the development of European culture.

The ancient period includes such terms as bronchus, herpes, carcinoma, coma, polypus, typhus, cholera, emphysema, epidemia (epidemia), aorta, trachea, diaphragma, phalanx, glaucoma, etc. The terminology of individual sciences consists of tens and hundreds of thousands of terms. However, as the system of scientific concepts and the corresponding terminology became more complex, the need began to be felt for a theoretical understanding of the mechanisms of terminology and the practical regulation of this process.

This is how the interdisciplinary branch of science came into being - term science. The starting point in terminology is that the terminology - briefly, precisely - simultaneously expresses a scientific concept. To do this, the terminology must satisfy several requirements: - adequacy: the content of the terminable concept must comply with modern scientific knowledge about the corresponding object; - accuracy: the terminable concept, in terms of its content and volume, must be strictly distinguished from other terms of the given terminology system; - univocality: any term must correspond to only one concept; Any concept must correspond to only one term.

In real-life terminology, not all terms meet these requirements. Therefore, specialists in other sciences, including medicine, pay great attention to the standardization of their professional science. Modern medicine represents a very branched and deeply differentiated industry in the country. Its terminological system consists of many subsystems, among which three leading ones stand out: anatomical terminology, pharmaceutical terminology, and medical terminology.

1. Names of functional disorders The names of functional disorders are usually compiled using a combination of prefixed and root elements. And prefix TEs most often use the prefix dys- in combination with the final root TE: dysgeusia, aef - dysgeusia, disorder of taste; dyskinesia, aef - dysfunction, disorder of coordinated motor acts. The following combination of the noun dysfunction, onis f - dysfunction is used: dysfunctio renum - kidney dysfunction The complete cessation of any function of the physiological process is expressed using the prefix a - (an - before a vowel): aphagia, aef - aphagia, complete inability to swallow; anuria, aef - anuria, failure of urine to enter the bladder. The absence of quality (function) is the inability to perform it, which is also indicated using the Latin prefix in- (im - before a labial consonant): insufficientia, aef - insufficiency : immobilitas, atis f - immobility This prefix is used in adjectives: immaturus, a, um - newly; incompletus, a, um - incomplete The

cessation of work (function) can result in a special noun term: collapsus, us m (Latin letters: “fall”, “decline”) - collapse, sudden cessation of work of an organ that is acutely reduced Yeah the amount of oxygen, blood and other factors.

2. The names of pathological processes and conditions The names of pathological processes and conditions are composed using prefectual, suffixal and root TEs, as well as the Latin noun term. At the same time, to noun terms a certain definition is often added, which characterizes the peculiarity of a given pathological process (acute, chronic, complete, partial, etc.). Almost all prefixes are used as prefectual TEs, but Greek prefixes are found much more often than Latin ones. Their meaning in maple terms usually coincides with their meaning in anatomical terms. However, often the Greek prefix in the composition of many terms determines the layer, since, firstly, the root morphemes of such terms are not used without prefixes in medical terminology, and secondly, The Greek prefix itself has a lot of meaning. Therefore, in such cases, it is necessary to assimilate the term without isolating the prefix in it and without conducting a morphological analysis of the word, for example: diabetes, ae m - diabetes, based on a group of a more endocrine nature, character There is excessive secretion of urine from the organ; diathesis, is f (Greek diathesis - predisposed) - diathesis, increased tendency of an organ to some more painful reactions to some kind of irritant; epilepsia, ae f - epilepsy, a chronic disease of the brain, accompanied by a sudden onset of seizures;

3. Pharmaceutical terminology and formulation The terms “pharmacist” and “pharmacy” from the ancient Greek origin go back to the word pharmakon medicine. The words pharmakeutike (implied pharmakeutiketechne, i.e. pharmaceutical art) and pharmakfa were used to mean “the skill of preparing and applying medicines to treat patients.” Subsequently, through Latin, these two terms were included in all languages of Europe. For many centuries, European medicine has traditionally used Latin and Latin Greek words in its raw materials for the production of medicines and in its prepared medicines. ε in specific recommendations for their use - in the recipe. Pharmaceutical terminology consists of the basis of medicines, dosage forms, as well as auxiliary words (verbs, nouns, adjectives, adverbs, prepositions), which are used mainly in recipes. Medicines are substances, a mixture of substances, officially approved for use in the treatment, prevention and diagnosis of diseases.

These products are obtained from plant, mineral and vegetable raw materials and are synthesized by synthetic means. All medicines are prepared in the so-called dosage forms (tablets, solutions, medicines, etc.), which are most convenient for receiving (using) these medicines. A medicine prepared in a pharmacy is a medicine prepared at a pharmaceutical facility in a dosage form - this is a medicine ready for use. In pharmaceuticals it is called "drug". The list of Latin dosage forms and drugs is the International Pharmaceutical Nomenclature. From time to time, as some drugs become outdated and other dosage forms become available, the list of pharmaceutical terms is reviewed and updated.

4. Uppercase and lowercase letters in dictionary form and as part of a pharmaceutical term. Capital letters appear both in dictionary form and as part of a term:

1. Named medicinal plants: Chamomilla, ae f - chamomile; FloresChamomillae - chamomile flower; Frangula, aef - wreck; DecoctumcorticisFrangulae - decoction of buckthorn bark.

2. Based on chemical elements - catheons: Ferrum, i n - elego; Sirupus Aloe scum Ferro - aloe syrup with gel; Strychninum, i n - strekhnen; SolutioStrychnininitratis - solution of strechnine nitrate.

3. Name of medicines: Prednisolonum, i n - prednisolone; TabulettaePrednisoloni - prednisolone tablet; Leonurus, im - motherwort; TincturaLeonuri - motherwort infusion.

4. Words equating to medicines: Amylum, i n - starch; Gelatina,ae f - Gelatin(a); Gelatosa, ae f - gelato; Propolisum, i n - propolis; Saccharum, i n - sugar; Talcum, i n - talc; Terebinthina, ae f - terpenten; Vaselinum, i n - vagelen, cf.: MucilagoAmyli - a trace of wheat starch; Oleum Terebinthinae - skepedar.

5. Clinical terminology Clinical terminology (from the Greek klinike (techne) - care for the sick) is the most extensive field of medical terminology. Here are presented the most common medical diseases - deviations from the norm, methods of research and treatment, clinical specialties and specialists. All these names are basically nouns.

Such nouns can be the same root word (asthma,atis n - asthma; hernia, ae f - grya; struma, ae f - gob). However, in most cases, it is layered in composition and consists mainly of Greek word-formative elements, termine elements (TE). A

termelement is considered to be any morphologically integral part of a word (prefix, root, base, suffix), which is included in many terms, preserving its orthographic complex and semantic meaning.

For example, the prefix hyper - appears in many terms, maintaining “above the norm”: hyperaesthesia - increased sensitivity; hyperthyreosis - increased function of the thyroid gland; hyperglykaemia - increased blood sugar levels. The Greek root derm- meaning “koya” is found in a whole range of terms, denoting medical pathological conditions of something (dermatitis, dermatosis, melanoderma, etc.). The suffix - itis denotes inflammatory processes in all terms: bronchitis - inflammation of the bronchi, colpitis - inflammation of the vagina, hepatitis - inflammation of the liver. Affective and root TEs are treated. Affective TEs are prefixes and suffixes. For example, the prefix hypo - forms terms with the meaning “not normal”: hypothermia - hypothermia, lower temperature, hypothermia; hypothyreosis - hypothyroidism, lower function of the thyroid gland; hypoxia - hypoxia, lower level of oxygen in tissues. The suffix - oma usually means “tumor”: lipoma, tumor of the lip tissue; odontoma - odontoma, tumor of the lip tissue. Root TEs are the roots of Greek, and sometimes Latin, nouns, adjectives and places.

It is customary to divide root TEs into initial and final ones. The initial TEs are connected to the suffix of the final TE. For example, TE angi - meaning “vessel” can be combined with the suffixam - itis еλε - oma in the terms angioma (angioma, tumor of the tissue of blood vessels) and angiitis (angitis, inflammation of the walls of blood vessels). At the same time, these TEs can be combined with root terminal TEs: angiosclerosis (angiosclerosis, thickening of the walls of blood vessels), angiospasmus (angiospasm, spasm of blood vessels). The initial TE is usually connected to another, including the final TE, using a connecting vowel - o -: bronchospasmus - bronchospasm, less of the bronchi bronchodilatatio - bronchodilation, dilatation of the bronchi E After the TE, to which the initial TE is connected, begins with a vowel, then the connecting ones - o -, as a rule, is skipped: nephrectomia - nephrectomy, an operation to remove the kidney melanuria - melanuria, the presence of a black pigment in the urine However, sometimes this rule is not observed and connectives - o - are preserved : acroaesthesia - acroesthesia, increased sensitivity of the lower parts of the body bronchoadenitis - bronchoadenitis,

inflammation of lymphatic areas around the bronchi bronchoectasia - bronchiecta, dilation of the lumen of the bronchi.

Root TEs can often act as both initial and final thermoelements, for example: nos- ε - nosis (illness, disease), cf.: nosologia, ae f - noologiya, the study of the forms of illness and its class; zoonosis is an infectious disease transmitted from animals to humans. In such cases, students are obliged to use both of these options and translate them into an oral or written answer: sick, sick - nos-, - nosis. Root TEs can connect with each other, forming multicomponent structures: chole (blister) + cyst (blister) -> cholecyst - (blister): cholecystographia - cholestography - radiography of the blister. ot (ear) + rhin (nose) + laryng (larynx) -> otorhinolaryng-: otorhinolaryngologia- otorhinolaryngologist, medical specialist, studying diseases of the ear, nose and throat. Some initial TEs appear in several versions, i.e. on a completely or incomplete basis: chromat- ε chrom-, haemat- chaem -: chromatopsia - chromatopsia, color rage; chromocystoscopia - chromocystoscope, examination of the bladder after the injection of a dye. haematuria - hematuria, blood in the urine. haemostasis - hemostasis, stopping bleeding. This phenomenon is due to the variability of thermoelements.

Root TEs can sometimes have several meanings. So, the initial TE kerat may have 2 beginnings: 1) cornea of the eye; 2) stratum corneum of the epidermis, cf.: keratitis - keratitis, inflammation of the cornea of the eye; kerotosis - keratosis, the common name for the disease, characterized by thickening of the stratum corneum of the epidermis. TE aden-has 3 meanings: relating to gels, gelled tissues of the epithelium; refers to adenoids; It should be remembered that when translating multi-word terms into Latin, the entire term must consist of at least two words - a noun with an adjective or a noun with a noun.

6. Terms and names of biomedical sciences, specialties and sections of clinical medicine in Navan sciences, specialties and medical departments are most often formed using the final TE - logia: ophthalmologia, ae f - ophthalmologist, medical department dedicated to this the disease and its treatment methods; physiologia, ae f - physiology, the science of natural processes in the body; stomatologia, ae f - dentistry, devoted to medicine dedicated to diseases of the oral cavity organs and methods of their treatment. Among similar sciences, the term pathologia stands out, which is used in two ways eex: section of medicine dedicated to the regularity of the causes of

disease processes; deviates from the norm. The latter is found in modern medicine more often than the first, and on its basis the adjective pathological (pathologicus, a, um) was coined - associated with a deviation from the norm, i.e. accompanying illness, illness.

As a final TE -pathologia is used for the formation of some branches of maple medicine: neuropathologia, ae f - neuropathology, section of maple medicine dedicated to nervous diseases systems and methods of their treatment; sexopathologia, ae f - sexopathologist, director of clinical medicine dedicated to sexual disorders and methods of treatment. Based on TE - logia, adjectives are formed with the final element - logicus, a, um (Russian equivalent - loge cheskes), which indicates belonging to some group sciences, the field of medicinal medicine, methods of research and treatment: bacteriologicus, and, um-bacteriological, relating to bacteriology - the science dedicated to the study of activity of the bacterium; pathologicus, a, um - pathological, associated with a deviation from the norm; traumatologicus, a, um - traumatological, intended for the treatment of injuries. Some ideas from the fields of clinical medicine are developed using the final TE - iatria:

geriatria, ae f - geriatrics, part of the maple medical literature dedicated to diseases of old age and methods of their treatment; psychiatria, ae f - psychiatrist, worked on clinical medicine, dedicated to psychiatric diseases and methods of their treatment. Individual terms are developed using the final TE - paedia:

logopaedia, ae f - speech therapist, department of pedagogy dedicated to the correction of speech defects; orthopaedia, ae f - orthopedics, a branch of clinical medicine dedicated to the correction of defects and deformities of the musculoskeletal system. Based on some sections of maple medicine, the formulas are dangerous: morbiinterni - internal pain; morbi infectiosi - infectious diseases 7. Names of specialists in biomedical sciences and clinical medicine. Most of the Latin specialists, both in the medical sciences and in the fields of clinical medicine, study using the final TE - logus: physiologus, im - physiologist, specialist in the field of physiology - the science of natural processes in the body; proctologus, im - proctologist, medical specialist in diseases directly from the doctor, some doctors-clinicians are treated with the help of TE - pathologus - iater, and such terms are always correlated with the name of the corresponding sections of maple medicine: neuropathologia, ae f - neuropathologist, im - neurologist, medical specialist in diseases of the peripheral

nervous system; paediatrica, ae f - paediatric, tri m - pediatrician, specialist in the treatment of childhood diseases

The Latin name of specialists, which in Russian equivalents have a final element - est, is a noun of the masculine gender of the I declension with a final element - ista: infectiousista - infectionista, ae m - specialist doctor Eats for infectious diseases. oculist -oculista, ae m (= ophthalmologus, i m) - a specialist in the treatment of eye diseases. According to this model, a Latin equivalent of the term “therapist” is compiled and equivalents of terms in which the word “therapist” acts as the final TE: therapist - therapeutista, ae m - a specialist in the treatment of internal diseases: psychotherape utista, ae m - specialist doctor in the field of psychotherapy - a method of treatment by treating a dog.

In a similar way, the Latin equivalents of the terms are constructed: diagnostician, speech therapist, orthopedist, orthodontist, pathologist, endoscopist: diagnosta, ae m - diagnostician, specialist in the diagnosis of diseases; endoscopista, ae m - endoscopist, a doctor who specializes in examining internal organs using an endoscope; logopaedista, ae m - speech therapist, specialist who corrects speech defects; orthopaedista, ae m - orthopedist, specialist in the correction of defects of the musculoskeletal system; orthodontista, ae m - orthodontist, dentist, correcting defects in the lips and jaws; pathoanatomista, ae m (= prosector, oris m) - pathologist, doctor, performing an autopsy on a corpse in order to determine the pathological change and confirm (or refute) the clinical analysis of death. Based on specialists who have in Russian equivalents the final element - path, which is a noun II declension with the final element - pathus: naturopath - naturopathus, i m - a doctor who uses only natural remedies for treatment (This is not true); osteopath - osteopathus, i m - a doctor who specializes in diseases of the human skeletal system.

We exclude from the meaning of the terms that are formed according to this model, the term psychopath - psychopathus, i m, denoting a person who is characterized by imbalance - mental instability Ex processes. Today, Latin is not only a memory of the philosophers, orators, and poets of Ancient Rome, but is an inalienable attribute of the modern world. Latin is firmly rooted in scientific terminology in many fields of science, especially in medicine, biology and prudence. Therefore, we will distinguish separately medical, biological and ardent Latin. In medicine, almost all medical terms have a Latin-Greek origin

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